

Impact of Strategic Management Accounting Practices on Corporate Performance in Vietnamese Agricultural Enterprises

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Abstract:

The organizations with strong level of intellectual capital should have developed management accounting with strategic directions that support such endeavors. In the history of IC accounting research, the focus of empirical studies has always been the direct relationship between intellectual capital components and corporate performance.

Keywords: *corporate performance, intellectual capital, strategic management accounting practices, Vietnamese agricultural enterprises*

1. Introduction

strategic management accounting is a form of management accounting which emphasis is placed on information which relates to key strategic decision ([CIMA, 2014a](#)). Simultaneously, following by resource- based theory, intellectual capital is the asset used for strategic purposes. Strategic management accounting would therefore appear to have a potential role to play in intellectual capital management. Notwithstanding the intellectual capital literature in accounting is varied but mainly addresses external reporting or the measurement or the valuation of such strategic assets, there has been little discussion on the two-way relationship between intellectual capital and strategic management accounting. Firstly, the organizations with strong levels of intellectual capital will have the assets as the necessary concrete to develop strategic management accounting system to support the managerial efforts in terms of identifying, measuring, and communicating the value drivers ([Tayles, Pike, & Saudah, 2007](#)). Secondly, once strategic management system has been evolved, it will address the issues of identifying, measuring, and communicating intellectual capital to support the strategic objectives. The challenge, therefore, is to devise a system of strategic management accounting practices that are in alignment with the unique attributes and the competitive strategies of the company. In other words, it must be possible to identify and value, with some precision, the component elements of the generic intellectual capital of the company. Furthermore, when analysing the Vietnamese transitional economic context, Vietnamese enterprises have gradually applied the advanced accounting techniques, in line with market mechanisms because many wholly foreign- owned enterprises established in Vietnam have been providing practical knowledge of strategic management accounting, which has been introduced to Vietnamese practitioners and scholars. Therefore, it is undeniable that medium and large enterprises in Vietnam do not have any understanding of how to implement strategic management accounting in their business operations. Not surprisingly, the issue of strategic management accounting thereby started to be studied in Vietnam since the 2010s.

2. Literature review

2.1. Review of international studies of strategic management accounting

In 1981, Simmonds published a paper in the UK professional magazine, Management Accounting, in which he presented a strong case for the adoption of strategic management accounting (SMA) (Simmonds, 1981). Many professional and academic papers continued this theme. Overall, the research continues to maintain four themes emphasizing on (1) how to define the concept of strategic management accounting, (2) what kinds of SMA techniques applied in a variety of industries, countries, (3) the impacts of strategy options on SMA changes and (4) strategic management accounting process (see in Appendix 2). Most of the published empirical research

over the past 30 years has consisted of questionnaire surveys that sought to establish the extent to which specific SMA techniques have been adopted (Langfield-Smith, 2008). However, the limitations of surveys and the relative dearth of case studies mean that very little is known about how the SMA techniques are used, by whom and for whom (Nixon & Burns, 2012).

2.2. Research on conceptualizing strategic management accounting

There is no agreed definition of SMA in the literature. At its very simplest, SMA is conceptualized as an approach that lies at the interface between strategic management and accounting (Roslender & Hart, 2003). According to Simmonds (1981)'s first definition, SMA can be generally defined as a generic approach that connects management accounting, strategy and strategic positioning of the company, while Bromwich (1990) provides a definition that limits SMA to financial information, but which is focused on performance relative to competitors. However, some other authors see marketing as the more relevant orientation for SMA (for example, Foster and Gupta (1994); Roslender (1995); Wilson (1995)). From the relevant literature, three main approaches in conceptualizing SMA can be distinguished as follows:

- Simmonds (1981)'s approach to SMA is based more on Porter's framework, which catalysed a stream of research, focusing more on cost management needed to support low price competitive strategy rather than design and innovation to earn a price premium through product differentiation. Thus, there is a demand of financial information about competitors to cope with core competitors' moves.
- Bromwich (1990)'s SMA approach is based on attribute costing technique, where the aim is to cost a product's benefit providing to customers, as opposed to the approach that determines reasons driving costs of product. Thus, there is a need of considering the benefits offered to customers, and how these contribute into building sustainable competitive advantage.
- On the perspective of marketing connecting to SMA, Roslender and Hart (2003) argue that SMA should become "more thoroughly infused with marketing issues, theories and concepts to form a marriage of equal partners". Thus, there is a necessity of "brand management accounting" that would include performance measures such as market share, market growth and brand strength, and customer profitability focusing on sub-brands and specific market offerings.

From the stated definitions, it is obvious that the terminology of SMA has a multitude of different interpretations, depending on the researchers' scientific background, underlying assumptions and starting points. Since Simmonds' first definition was introduced over 30 years ago, there is little agreement what is and what constitutes SMA. This term itself is opening to a number of interpretations due to varied nature of research associated with it, while some researchers has emphasized the interface between accounting and marketing, while others pay more attention on linkages to strategy. The 1990s are described as "the glory decade" where academics, consultants and practitioners all played a role in popularizing strategic accounting (Langfield-Smith, 2008). Shank and Govindarajan (1993) note that many SMA techniques has been implemented as pilot studies in US companies and published as teaching case studies, or as chapters in books. Professional journals carried articles with SMA themes and the training activities of professional accounting bodies focused on SCM tools and techniques (Langfield-Smith, 2008). Global consulting firms developed very active practices in the field of SMA and thereby the SMA term, due to the absence of generally conceptual framework, ranges in its definitions from narrow ones (competitor-focused and performance measurement practices) to the umbrella under the viewpoint of "external orientation".

2.3. Research on strategic management accounting techniques

When it comes to SMA practices, due to the absence of generally conceptual framework, there is a multitude of listing and propositions of various accounting techniques that have strategic focus. As can be seen in Appendix 2, there are significant overlaps between the classifications of SMA techniques, whereas the differences exist in

customer accounting and strategic accounting. Despite the differences in research viewpoints, the groups of SMA techniques such as strategic cost accounting, competitor accounting and strategic accounting are widely accepted as the components of SMA practices. Until 2001, Guilding and McManus (2002)'s research adds 3 customer-focused techniques that may be referred to as the fourth dimension "customer accounting".

2.4. Review of studies investigating the relationship between strategic management accounting practices and corporate performance

The accumulated body of evidence also suggests that tailoring an organisation's strategic management accounting control system to its strategy may result in enhanced performance. Most empirical work in this area assumes a contingency approach. Contingency theory assumes the expectation that there is a structural design that best fits a given strategy and hence results in highest performance (Cadez & Guilding, 2012). Thereby, many studies, based on contingency theory, have examined the relationship amongst strategy, SMA practices and corporate performance. The start point of the empirical research on the correlation between SMA practices and performance is the work of Chenhall and Langfield-Smith (1998) in the research scope of Australian companies.

Chenhall and Langfield-Smith (1998) discover that there are positive associations between performance and a range of SMA practices, under various strategic orientations. The following studies also find a positive direct relationship between SMA practices and corporate performance or perceived strategy moderating the positive correlation between SMA practices and firm performance. For instances, Aykan and Aksoylu (2013) discover the effects of competitive strategies and strategic management accounting techniques on the perceived qualitative and quantitative performance of medium and large size businesses in Kayseri, Turkey. In similarity, Al-Mawali and Al-Shammari (2013) conducted an empirical investigation into the relations among strategic management accounting, perceived environmental uncertainty and organizational performance in 296 companies in Jordan. The results indicated that the level of SMA usage positively affect organizational performance, and perceived environmental uncertainty moderates this relationship (Al-Mawali & Al-Shammari, 2013). Alternatively, SMA practices are examined in association with one of the perspectives of corporate performance. It is evidenced by Ramljak and Rogošić (2012) who realized that the synergistic effect of the different strategic management accounting techniques implementation has a positive impact on cost control and reduction. In another research, in spite of using contingency theory, Cadez and Guilding (2012) deploys a holistic configurational approach to examine the relationship between strategy, strategic management accounting, and performance. Configurations are derived empirically, using an inductive approach, from a sample of 109 manufacturing companies. The study of Cadez and Guilding (2012) suggest that high SMA technique usage levels and greater involvement of accountants in strategy processes are more congruent with a dynamic prospector type strategy, leading higher performance.

In generally, the correlation between SMA practices and corporate performance has been conducted in a range of countries such as Australian (Chenhall & Langfield-Smith, 1998), UK (Ma & Tayles, 2009), Malaysian (Hassan, Muhammad, & Ismail, 2011), Croatia (Ramljak & Rogošić, 2012), Slovenian (Cadez & Guilding, 2012), Jordan (Al-Mawali & Al-Shammari, 2013) and the exact nature of this positive correlation is consistent in all of studies.

Although the correlation between SMA practices and performance has been examined in many studies within many countries, the research methodology of this issue seems to be unchanged. In majority, the studies use the question "To what extent does your organization use the following techniques?" and the SMA techniques were listed together with a Likert-type scale ranging from "1" (not at all), to "7" (to a great extent). In term of corporate performance, each manager was asked to evaluate her/his company's performance level by comparing it with the major competitor on financial and non- financial performance indicators. Managers respond to each of the items of performance on a seven-point Likert scale anchored at both ends such that, 1 = Poor and 7 = Excellent. The extent to which the various SMA techniques are measured via using the questions, which are

frequently used as being introduced by Cravens and Guilding (2001) and Guilding and McManus (2002). However, there is a lack of study concerning the combination between data created by survey in terms of SMA techniques and financial data regarding corporate performance. In some studies such as Ma and Tayles (2009), the case study method is applied to explore the issues which surround change and which enable the adoption of SMA and the repositioning of management accountants to become more strategic, leading to enhanced performance.

In terms of research venue, most of the studies on intellectual capital and SMA practices have been conducted in developed Western countries and some of Asian countries such as China, Malaysia, Taiwan, Hong Kong rather than in Asian developing countries with the transitional economy – Vietnam. Vietnam may differ from Western countries in terms of culture, economy and political environment that influence the progress of IC development (Nga & Thomas, 2005) as well as the orientations how to implement strategic management accounting (Loi, 2014). Concerning the relationship between culture and strategic management accounting, collectivism in Vietnam confronted individualism in the West. Therefore, it raises the question if the national culture of collectivism really distinguishes the Vietnamese style of strategic management accounting implementation from that adopted in the West. Although there are many international studies confirming the benefits of strategic management accounting, to the best of my knowledge, there are currently no empirical studies that directly investigate the link between strategic management accounting practices and corporate performance in Vietnamese context. Therefore, a study on the impacts of SMA practices on Vietnamese enterprises' performances can contribute into the understandings of whether the benefits of SMA may be performed in the transitional economy as consistently as in the Western contexts.

On the other hand, although research in the extant literature has primarily focused on the value relevance and the market valuation of intellectual capital in many other countries (e.g. Ming-Chin et al. (2005); Mondal and Ghosh (2012); Cleary (2015)), the performance of intellectual capital remains empirically under-explored in the context of Vietnam. More specially, Vietnamese empirical cross-sectional studies of the performance implication of intangible investments or intellectual capital are scarce probably due to two main difficulties. Firstly, Vietnamese enterprises often do not provide a comprehensive account for intangible investments. Much of the expenditures in this category are expensed rather than capitalized. Disclosure on those expenditures is also severely inadequate. Secondly, because Vietnamese managers have not actually realized the critical value of intellectual capital in their managing process, such a business environment having no more concern about intellectual capital may not boost the wave of IC research in Vietnam. As evidence of this, few researchers in Vietnam have addressed the issue of performance implication of intellectual capital. Therefore, the studies on intellectual capital as well as strategic management accounting in the context of an Asian country, the case of Vietnam with the transitional economy, can add more insight to the literature

3. Methodology

This study first reviews the literature related to intellectual capital, strategic management accounting practices, corporate performance before proposing two research models with six hypotheses.

Due to the complex of the research models with mediators and a small sample size context, data analysis is conducted by applying partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) with the support of SPSS 24.0 and SmartPLS 3.1 software packages.

Fig.1. Research model

PLS-SEM can easily handle reflective and formative measurement models, as well as single-item constructs, with no identification problems (Hair Jr & Hult, 2016). It can therefore be applied in a wide variety of research situations. When applying PLS- SEM, the author also benefits from high efficiency in handling constructs measured with single-item measure (i.e. Assets turnover, ROE, Tobin q) and multi-item measures (i.e. measures of the variables of SMA practices).

PLS-SEM is the non-distribution used technique to analyse multivariate data, as a consequence, PLS-SEM does not initially provide t-values to evaluate the estimates' significance (Hair Jr & Hult, 2016). Instead, researchers have to rely on the non-parametric bootstrapping procedure that provide bootstrap standard errors. Additionally, the bootstrapping procedure allows researchers to assess the stability and the significance of outer weight, outer loadings and path coefficients and thereby report their values with a greater degree of accuracy (Kline, 2011). Bootstrapping is the re-sampling approach that draws random sample with replacement from the original data and then uses these samples to estimates path coefficients in multiple times under slightly changed data constellation (Hair Jr & Hult, 2016). The number of bootstrap samples should be high, but must be at least equal to the number of valid observations in the dataset that are gathered. As the thumb rule, bootstrapping should be performed on 5,000 bootstrap samples at the level of 95% confidence (Hair Jr & Hult, 2016). For example, if the original sample is 200 valid observations, then each of the 5,000 bootstrap samples should contain 200 randomly chosen observations.

4. Empirical results

The majority of the results generated strongly support previous studies which considered the positive relationship between SMA practices and corporate performance. Specifically, the following four beta-path coefficients are found to be both positive and statistically significant at a p value less than 0.01 in all four models tested – asset turnover (beta = 0.511, p value = 0.000), investment efficiency (beta = 0.724, p value = 0.000), return on equity (beta = 0.806, p value = 0.000) and Tobin q (beta = 0.653, p value = 0.000). It appears that Vietnamese publicly traded enterprises still generally favour the use of SMA practices to make operational and strategic decisions. As such firms continue to expand and mature, they are implementing more sophisticated management accounting systems to cater for their increasingly sophisticated managerial information requirements. SMA practices are thus contributing into the enhancement of productivity, financial performance and firm value.

On the other hand, compared with the other studies, some suggest that SMA may be at risk of losing its privileged position as the information provider for subsequent managerial decision making to improve corporate

performance (Cleary, 2015) because much techniques are occurring outside of the accounting function (Anderson, 2007) and a combination of factors such as heightened pressures for enhanced internal controls and fraud detection (Langfield-Smith, 2008). However, the results of this study confirm the effective role of SMA practices in Vietnamese public enterprises until now. Since Vietnam's open-door policy has been generating many the wholly-foreign-owned enterprises established in Vietnam during the last two decades, such firms bring knowledge of SMA introduced to Vietnamese practitioners, thereby foreign managers are changing into much of innovative notions generally improving corporate performance better than the traditional viewpoint of management accountants.

Hypothesis	Structural relationship	path	Expected sign	Direct effect	<i>t</i> value	Significance (p < 0.1)?	Test result
H	ATO □ SMA		+	0.511	4.310	***	Support
	INVEFF □ SMA		+	0.724	8.447	***	Support

5. Conclusion

In terms of whether the level of IC within firms are influenced by strategic accounting-based approaches, this study finds that firms with higher levels of human and structural capital attach greater importance to strategic costing approaches such as “Strategic pricing, Strategic costing, Brand valuation and Capital budgeting”, as shown in Table 6.6.

In more details, pricing is complex, and companies need to invest resources, infrastructure and processes to enable to set the right price at the right time, any time. On one perspective, the available intellectual capital firstly impacts pricing strategic capability. An effective pricing process cannot be run on automatic pilot. It requires well-trained people (human capital) who understand the company in all its complexities such as its strategy, range of products, customers, suppliers and competitors. Companies can have any number of dedicated people involved in pricing decisions, but those people will not be fully effective if the organization is systems poor. This means that the pricing process requires structural capital to support it. Developing human capital and structural capital are two important steps to build the effective process of pricing. However, companies will still lack the strategic capability if they have not invested in relational capital. In fact, anticipating and managing customers' responses to the changes of price level may be the most cost-effective element of pricing capability. On the other hand, the strategy pricing is an effective tool used to manage intellectual capital. Given that if a company chooses a cost leadership strategy, managers must be aware that their company has the advantage of structural capital, which is reflected in the efficient production process to ensure cost savings. As a result, managers must continually improve their production processes to protect the firm's position of cost leadership. Developing an effective process of strategic pricing requires a firm to effectively manage human capital by training existing employees or by hiring the professional employees who bring pricing expertise with them.

With respect to strategic costing, it is the approach which is vital to manage a firm's structural capital and relational capital. To understand a firm's strategic costs, strategic costing is used as a management accounting approach by the usage of cost database with strategic information to develop and identify customers, stakeholders, and regulators costs that will bring a sustainable competitive advantage. Customer costs stem from efforts to bring on new customers and service existing ones. Stakeholder costs stem from efforts by human resources, purchasing, finance, and public relations to transact business with employees, suppliers, and investors. Regulatory costs include those imposed by state, federal, and local municipalities, as well as public safety and other governmental oversight agencies. Such these costs contribute into the creation of relational capital. Thus, in order to develop relational capital, management accountants and financial managers should identify and shift costs from the burgeoning elective costs category (i.e. are self-imposed and are mostly procedural or infrastructural in nature) to the under resourced strategic costs category to achieve the optimal mix of spending. These spendings typically focus on developing new products and markets and include cross-functional efforts to expand existing sources of revenue via increased customer retention, referrals, and repeat buying.

Tayles et al. (2007) suggests that traditional appraisal techniques are no longer appropriate for intangible investments given the non-financial benefits and inter-related cost complexity that exists. Mouck (2000) argues that “The traditional capital budgeting model is virtually useless for the high-tech, knowledge-based, increasing returns sectors of the economy”. Increasingly, firms less in tangible assets, and more in intangibles are hard to justify when using conventional capital budgeting tools (Irani, Ezingard, & Grieve, 1998). The growing literature considers real options which extends the traditional capital budgeting approach by providing a more appropriate evaluation of strategic investments (Tayles et al., 2007). High IC firms that have invested heavily in innovation will be in a better position to exploit future opportunities, as yet unidentified. These strategic options would include such areas as entering new markets, development of follow-on products, and development of brand extension. Traditional discounted cash flow models do not capture the value of options embedded in corporate decisions (Tayles et al., 2007). The high structural capital firms are more likely to have capital investment systems that capture the costs and benefits of intangibles. Thus, they are also more likely to use a real options approach and accept projects where the financial appraisal does not support such action. According to Tayles et al. (2007), there was evidence in Malaysian high IC firms, with a strong focus on managerial creativity (human capital), innovation, intellectual property, knowledge embedded in information technology (structural capital) and stakeholders relationship (relational capital), typically possess considerable strategic flexibility, they place less reliance on conventional capital budgeting approaches such as net present value but follow-on options are more easily identifiable.

Last but not least, brand is one of the elements of relational capital, thus brand management is a part of IC management. The creation and maintenance of brands are becoming more important in today’s intensely competitive environment. Investing in branding activities creates brand equity. Equity exists when the customers are aware of brand, loyal to the brand and perceive the brand as having quality. Awareness, loyalty and quality perception are three main components of successful brand. Brand valuation in financial terms is the assessment of brand strength factors so as managers to manage them. Once brand is managed better, a firm’s relational capital is also upward.

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